

Impact Of Transformational Leadership Style On Job Performance, Job Satisfaction And Organizational Learning

Jalil Ahmed Thebo, Qasim Ali Shah, Juned Ali Shah, Imran Ahmed Shah, Hassan Jawad Soomro, Ghulam Akbar Khaskheli

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 28, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 29, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Transformational leadership, Job Performance, Job satisfaction, Organizational learning.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5110585</p>	<p><i>To run any organization flourishingly most treasures assets are human resources. Capable and well-educated employers are considered crucial part for organization's success. Modern age has become globalized village where competencies between companies are scaled in terms of competent human resources. It is relatively difficult to handle people with different background, ethnicity, culture and religion. Leadership style comes handy in this regard. Leadership enables people to work in single platform. Organizations now days are more concerned about development, enhancing their leadership style. Now more and more organizations move towards modern approach of leadership called transformational leadership. Transformational leadership provides vision, cultivate hope, increase their communication horizon, and enable workers to think innovatively. All these factors lead towards organizational learning, job performance and job satisfaction. Job satisfaction helps to create positive image on employees, boost their morale and enhance innovate thinking. The employer who is satisfied with his job tends to remain loyal to their company. Job performance helps to create profitable organization in terms of monetary value as well as positive impact on organization. Transformational leadership style increases higher job performance which results in lower turnout ratio. Organizational learning increases when employees have trust, commitment and dedication towards work. Transformational leadership helps these goals to achieve effectively and efficiently. Employee motivation is the degree of vitality, duty, and imagination that an organization's laborers bring to their occupations. Regardless of whether the economy is developing or contracting, discovering approaches to spur workers is constantly an administration concern. The objective of research is to study effect of transformational leadership on organizational learning, job performance and job satisfaction with employee motivation. For this purpose we have taken multiple organizations across Karachi (Pakistan).</i></p>

Introduction

The impact of transformative leadership is checked on three dependent variables with one mediator "Employee Motivation". Those three dependent variables are: organizational learning, job satisfaction and job performance. Transformational leadership is the capability of the leader to inspire employees through motivation, consideration, intellect and idealized influence (Bass B., 1997) the first variable is organizational learning. Organizational learning is a technique where data is gathered, coordinated and analyzed to enhance organization growth (Choudhary, Akhtar, & Zaheer, 2013) the second dependent variable is job performance. Job performance is explained as the behaviors and execution of the employees that contribute to organizational performance (Rotundo & Sackett, 2002). Job performance holds a direct relationship with transformative leadership as effectively the leadership style is implemented then job performance is also effective in showing organizational progress making it one of the key variables. The third dependent variable is job satisfaction. It is defined as the reactions of employees to the job they are doing based on various elements (Fields, 2002). In this research the reaction is based on the transformative leadership style and its impact. High job satisfaction shows effective leadership style and low job satisfaction shows the ineffectiveness of the leadership style and therefore a good factor in understanding transformative leadership for employees. The mediator is Employee motivation. Employee motivation at work is considered as an essential drive as it generates effort and action towards work-related activities, for example, employee's willingness to spend the energy to achieve a common goal or reward. When an employee is motivated, he or she shows enthusiasm and eagerness towards the work and a strong determination to implement and accomplish the work tasks (Moran, 2013).

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

Employees are the most important assets for any organization. To handle the employees who have different backgrounds, ethnicity, religion and culture, the effective leadership is necessary in this regard. The aim of this research is to identify the impact of transformational leadership style on organizational learning, job satisfaction and job performance through employee motivation. Independent variable of this research is transformational leadership style and dependent variable of this research is organizational performance, job satisfaction and job performance and the mediator is Employee motivation.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The research emphasizes on the significance of leadership in an organization. In today's competitive setting, the organizations are expanding internationally and facing difficulties and challenges in achieving their aims and objectives. Leadership style affects each and every person within the organization be it top management or the low-level employees. Employee performance is recognized as performing assigned tasks, meeting the deadlines, Teambuilding. Employee performance which plays an essential part in company's growth; is heavily dependent on the leadership style used by the senior management. Leadership refers to the method of motivating the activities of an organized group towards the achievement of better Goals. Various organizations need strong styles of leadership to be practiced so that it encourages the Performance of workers. It is believed that the leader should not only lead the team but also be Effective. Therefore, the idea of this study will be to assess on how much employee performance is affected by the leadership style chosen by the management of an organization.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The answers of following questions will be provided in this research:

- How does transformational leadership style affect the organizational learning?
- How does transformational leadership style impact on job performance?
- How does job satisfaction is effected by transformational leadership style?

HYPOTHESIS

H1. Transformational leadership style has impact on organizational learning.

H2. Transformational leadership style has impact on job performance.

H3. Transformational leadership style has impact on job satisfaction.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to (Astuti, Aunnurahman, & Wahyudi, 1 March 2019) leadership style is the procedure and strategy for influencing individuals, give direction and executing plans. Laissez-faire, democratic and autocratic is the 3 novel sorts of style of pioneers as per various experts. In autocratic initiative decisions are made by pioneers without the subordinate's incorporation. Curiously, pioneers having an evenhanded democratic style before taking decisions to guide their subordinates and the pioneers who empower subordinates to choose decisions and therefore doesn't demonstrate administration attributes isolated from their positions are seen as lesser-faire (Ullah, Kiran, & Lui, 2019). Autocratic are the people who are overpowering in their organization, all power starts and completes with them. These pioneers or administrators trust they are superior to anything their subordinates in contemplations and considerations and think including subordinates while choosing decisions would consume a great deal of time and it isn't commendable enough to include them. (Joshi, March 1, 2019) Stated that leadership style of a pioneer or director would rely upon the circumstances and sort of the group leader is driving. For example, if the conditions require for moment acts the style of a leader would pursue the autocratic style of administration and would emit duties which the pioneer would should have been trailed by its supporters without inquisitive the reason. This is a class of aggressive leadership and it supported to spare period in earnest circumstance. Actually, the pioneer may likewise have the majority rule democratic style and focus on the view and vision of the adherents yet act what the brain says or what they accept to be right. Hardly any pioneer or supervisors may be very participative and takes the choice after a mutual consent understanding among the people of the gathering. Each style region embraced by pioneers in a differing condition and the fundamental goal of the considerable number of styles of initiative is to achieve the desired targets (Glynn & DeJordy, 2010). However, there are different authority styles yet the fundamental initiative styles that could be consider under the study are transformational, situational leadership style and democratic. The pioneers seeking after the ethical leadership initiative sort ceaselessly takes the moral choice and furthermore drives their workers morally. Correspondingly, the pioneers following ethical administration had the tough capacity to surrender their personal responsibility and inner self with the goal of accomplishing the goal (Antonakis & Day, 2017). These kinds of pioneers bolster the remark to evaluate their performance in the association all the more fairly rather than different pioneers or administrators and think of them as responsible and in charge of their deeds by and by for the deed of the representatives. Correspondingly, the deeds of a pioneer following ethical initiative style is dependent on the evaluations that satisfactory the arrangement of conviction of social benchmarks and

cultural values. This segment makes the ethical chief or pioneer a wide thought than the others and that the ethical head is built not just from the individual characteristics, properties, and charm yet the feelings, gauges, social and social characteristics are furthermore basic structure keys of ethical pioneer (Renz & Herman, 10 August 2016). According to (Cho, Shin, Billing, & Bhagat, 2019) the people who separated the Transformational just as Transactional initiative style, the transactional leadership is subject to trade resources with an arrangement to make the work finished For instance, a transactional pioneer offers specific compensations for the specialists on the off chance that they can support the pioneer or administrator to procure the objectives. Transactional pioneer induces the 2 wants, first is simply the desire of group and second is self-desire of the people of the group. Then again, the transformational pioneer slanted to influence the mindset's of individuals' and persuade them to offer less importance to their individual purposes and requirements for the wants and goals of the group (Farahnak, Ehrhart, Torres, & Aarons, 2019). The heavenly model is the commercial and welfare firms. Besides, the partners (clients, providers, workers) of these associations needs the activity to be finished however welfare organizations are not ready to satisfy the merchants, despite what might be expected, the business associations be slanted to exploit the abundance of its sellers.

The distinctive arrangement of leadership is known to be the valid administration which went to some degree against the possibility of ethical initiative, in light of the way that the effective pioneer act subject to their very own characteristics, emotions and feelings Authentic pioneers presents moral awareness, because of this care they can all the more promptly portray values precisely and thusly their exercises and words are balanced, it has been expressed that the clarification of pioneers conduct is much of the time required during the misfortune in ethics (Lagowska, Jacob, Sobral, & Goldszmidt, 2018 July). Be that as it may, (Ko, Ma, Haney, & Kang , 2018) communicated that Authentic pioneers is an instance of mind blowing uprightness, dependability, and great characteristics, moreover these pioneers see their lacks and individual limits and as needs be doesn't grasp the guarded strategy for association issues. Characteristics and morals could be impeded, and Unethical and good conduct should be perceived by pioneers

METHODOLOGY

VARIABLES

Followings are the variables of our study

Independent variable: Transformational leadership style

Dependent variable: Organizational learning, Job performance, Job satisfaction

Mediator variable: Employee motivation

To find the effect of transformational leadership style on organizational learning with employee motivation

To find the effect of transformational leadership style on job performance with employee motivation

To find the effect of transformational leadership style on job satisfaction (Joshi, March 1, 2019 ; Rubin, 2012)with employee motivation

DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENT

We will construct a survey which will include a questionnaire based on the Likert Scale. This will be used as a data collection instrument in this study.

DEDUCTIVE VERSUS INDUCTIVE APPROACH

The main difference between inductive and deductive approaches to research is that whilst a deductive approach is aimed and testing theory, an inductive approach is concerned with the generation of new theory emerging from the data.

DEDUCTIVE:

- ❖ GENERAL TO SPECIFIC ("top-down" approach)
- ❖ CONFIRMATION OR TESTING OF THEORY
- ❖ MOSTLY FOINDUCTIVE

INDUCTIVE:

- ❖ SPECIFIC TO GENERAL ("bottom up" approach)
- ❖ DEVELOP GENERAL CONCLUSIONS OR THEORIES
- ❖ MOSTLY FOR QUALITATIVE RESEARCH

SAMPLING DESIGN

The most common reason for using no probability sampling is that it is cheaper than probability sampling and can often be implemented more quickly (Battaglia, 2008).

PROBABILITY VERSUS NON PROBABILITY SAMPLING

Sampling means selecting a particular group or sample to represent the entire population. Sampling methods are majorly divided into two categories probability sampling and non-probability sampling. In the first case, each member has a fixed, known opportunity to belong to the sample, whereas in the second case, there is no specific probability of an individual to be a part of the sample. The two main methods used in survey research are probability sampling and non-probability sampling. The big difference is that in probability sampling all persons have a chance of being selected, and results are more likely to accurately reflect the entire population. While it would always be nice to have a probability-based sample, other factors need to be considered (availability, cost, time, what you want to say about results).

SAMPLE AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

A sample of 220 individuals from the organization employees was taken for this research. The research was conducted in Karachi which is a major city of Pakistan.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE

1. Reliability analysis/ technique
2. Correlation analysis/ technique
3. Regression analysis/ technique

DEMOGRPHIC PROFILE

Demographics	Frequency	Percent	
Age	Below 25	54	24.54
	25-30	103	46.81
	31-35	46	20.9
	36-40	13	5.9
	46 and above	4	1.8
Gender	Male	149	67.7
	Female	71	32.3
Highest education qualification	Bachelor	92	41.8
	Master	105	47.7
	PhD	23	10.6
	Total	220	100.0

Table 1

INTERPRETATION

This research study consists of 67.7% of males and 32.3% of females. According to this demographic profile 24.54% are of below 25 age, 46.81% lies in the age bracket of 25-30, 20.9% fell in the range of 31-35 year and 1.8% of people are of age 46 and above. When it comes to the highest education qualification of respondents 41.8% respondents have bachelor's degree, 47.7% of respondents have master's degree, and 10.6% are the one who have done their PhD.

DATA ANALYSIS VIA PLS-SEM

Data analysis has done by using partial least squares (Smart-PLS) which is a variance-based, structural equation modelling (SEM) technique and deals with multiple regressions modelling (Henseler, 2016).

Measurement Model Evaluation

Reflective Measurement Model Evaluation

Table 4.3 specifies reliability of reflective constructs. Reliability is measured by means of Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability. The threshold for Cronbach's alpha is 0.704 (Taber, 2016). And the threshold for composite reliability is 0.700 (Hair et al., 2017). Since all values of Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability are above the minimum threshold, hence reliability of construct is established.

Reliability Analysis of Reflective Constructs

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Employee motivation	0.791	0.878
Job performance	0.758	0.845
Job satisfaction	0.853	0.900
Organizational learning	0.712	0.822
Transformational leadership	0.825	0.884

Convergent Validity of Reflective Constructs

	Average Variance Extracted(AVE)
Employee motivation	0.705
Job performance	0.578
Job satisfaction	0.692
Organizational learning	0.536
Transformational leadership	0.657

Discriminant Validity of Reflective Constructs

0	Employee motivation	Job performance	Job satisfaction	Organizational learning	Transformational leadership
Transformational leadership					
Organizational learning	0.646	0.289	0.638	0.677	0.810
Job satisfaction	0.615	0.341	0.657	0.732	
Job performance	0.653	0.311	0.832		
	0.359	0.760			

Employee motivation 0.840

STRUCTURAL MODEL EVALUATION

The research analysis which carries out by structural path analysis model tests the hypothesis empirically. Figure 4.2 displays that the analysis starts from direct paths between independent and dependent variables. Furthermore, through this model's evaluation degree of variation in purchase intention is explained (Bagozzi, & Yi, 1988). Structural model also exhibits the contribution of brand consciousness, experiential, social influence, and trait of vanity in purchase intention

R SQUARE VALUE

The value of R square in the prescribed model for Employee motivation, job performance, job satisfaction and Organizational learning is 0.417, 0.129, 0.427, 0.379 respectively which is showing that to what extent Job performance, organizational learning and Job satisfaction area effecting Transformational leadership variation. Since the value is in between 0.3 & 0.7 it is considered as moderate explanatory power (Hair et al., 2017).

Table 4.6
R square values of Endogenous Variables

Endogenous Variable	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Employee motivation	0.417	0.415
Job performance	0.129	0.125
Job satisfaction	0.427	0.424
Organizational learning	0.379	0.376

EFFECT SIZE (F SQUARE)

The values of F square in the prescribed model is more its threshold i.e. 0.15. So, the strength of brand consciousness, experiential, social influence, and trait of vanity in explaining purchase intention is good (Hair et al., 2016).

Figure 4.3 T-values

Table 4.7 indicates path coefficients of t-value & p-value. Since t-values are greater than

1.64 & p-values are less than 0.05 (Hassan M. U, 2001). Hence, hypotheses H1, H2, H3 & H4 are supported.

Table 4.7

Path Coefficients of t-value & p-value

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Decision
EM -> JP	0.359	0.367	0.067	5.331	0.000	Supported
EM->JS	0.653	0.656	0.048	13.649	0.000	Supported
EM-> OL	0.615	0.620	0.050	12.377	0.000	Supported
TL-> EM	0.646	0.649	0.048	13.485	0.000	supported

Table 4.36 exhibits moderation analysis. According to which all H5, H6 and H7 are Supported. Since t-values are more than 1.64 & p-values are less than 0.05 (Hassan M. U, 2001)

Moderation Analysis

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Decision
TL->EM->JP	0.232	0.238	0.050	4.656	0.000	Supported

TL->EM- >JS	0.422	0.427	0.054	7.784	0.000	Supported
TL->EM- >OL	0.398	0.404	0.052	7.694	0.000	Supported

CONCLUSION

Efficiency of an organization relies on the job satisfaction, job performance, and organizational learning and escort to developing benefits. Transformational leadership, a methodology of improved relational connection among director and subordinate, is an approach to make larger amount of job satisfaction and organizational duty of workers. Transformational leadership additionally helps representatives to turn out to be progressively imaginative, inventive and bring such new thoughts which enable the association to develop intensely and adjust to the changing outside condition. This examination gives factually critical proof of the connections and the effects of transformational leadership styles on organization performance and satisfaction. Administration specialists propose that having a solid, positive vision of things to come assumes a basic job. In addition to the fact that it is essential to have faith in this vision yourself, you've additionally got the opportunity to rouse others to become tied up with your vision too. Being real, passionate, steady, and reliable are on the whole key attributes that will help rousing devotees to help your objectives for the gathering. The investigation proposes that the outcomes are significant and can help organizations create administration preparing programs that can be utilized to educate transformational authority abilities. Securing relational abilities, for example, settling clashes in the working environment and perceiving the requirements of representatives are a significant piece of transformational authority.

LIMITATIONS

This research also includes some limitations which are that it is only limited to the organization sector of one city which is Karachi, Pakistan with limited cultural context and therefore may not be effective in other cities or countries. Another thing is that with changing times leadership style may not be effective therefore its effectiveness may change with time. The third limitation is that there may be self-reported surveys in this meaning respondents may have given answers they thought were socially acceptable. Along with these limitations the study took a restricted sample size and having a higher sample size may show variation in the results. This study cannot be applicable to non-profit organizations nor other sectors such as manufacturing or textile industry.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The results show how transformational leadership effects job satisfaction, job performance and organizational learning which gives managers insight on how to improve employee performance as well as improve relationship with the employees as to increase organizational productivity and profitability. This study was conducted on organization sector and therefore similar research can also be conducted in other sectors as well as non-profit organizations to see if similar or different the results come out to be. The impact of transformational leadership can also be checked on other variables such as innovation and extra-role behaviors in order to better understand its impact on employee performance. The components of this leadership such as trust and ethical conduct can also be used to see how they impact the three dependent variables used in this research.

References

- Amitay, M., Popper, M., & Lipshitz, R. (2005). Leadership styles and organizational learning in community clinics. *The Learning Organization*, 12 (1), 57-70.
- Andersen. (2016). An Old Man and The "Sea of Leadership". *Journal of Leadership Studies*, 9, 70-81.
- Antonakis, J., & Day, D. (2017). *The nature of Leadership*. Sage Publication.
- Astuti, F., Aunnurahman, A., & Wahyudi, W. (1 March 2019). The Effect of Democratic Autocratic and Laissez-Faire (Free) Leadership Style of Kindergarten Headmaster toward Teacher Discipline Performance at Kindergartens in Southeast Pontianak District. *Education, Teaching and Learning*, 130-138.
- Avolio, B. J., & Gardner, W. L. (2005). Authentic leadership development. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 315-338.
- Avolio, B., & Yammarino, F. (2013). Introduction to, and overview of, transformational and charismatic leadership. In *Transformational and Charismatic Leadership: The Road Ahead 10th Anniversary Edition*. Emerald Group Publishing Limited.
- Avolio, B. J., & Bass, B. M. (2002). *Lawrence Erlbaum Associates*.

- Bass, B. (1997). Personal selling and transactional/transformational leadership. *Journal of Personal Selling & Sales Management*, 17(3), 19-28.
- Bass, B. M. (1990). "From transactional to transformational leadership: learning to share the vision. *Organizational Dynamics*, 18, 19-31.
- BONO, J., & JUDGE, T. (2003). SELF-CONCORDANCE AT WORK. *Academy of Management Journal*, 46, 554-571.
- Boyne, G., Poole, M., & Jenkins, G. (1999). Human resource management in the public and private sectors: An empirical comparison. *Public Administration*, 77(2), 407-420.
- Choudhary, A., Akhtar, S., & Zaheer, A. (2013). Impact of transformational and servant leadership on organizational performance: A comparative analysis. *Journal of business ethics*, 116(2), 433-440.
- Choudhary, A., Akhtar, S., & Zaheer, Z. (2013). impact of transformational and servant leadership on organizational learning. *journal of business ethics*, 116(2), 433-440.
- Conger, J., & Kanungo, R. (1994). Charismatic leadership in organizations: Perceived behavioral attributes and their measurement. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 15(5), 439-452.
- Conger, J., & Kanungo, R. (1998). Charismatic leadership in organization. *sage publications* .
- Cooper, D. (2015, Feb). Effective Safety Leadership. *safety Management*.
- crawford, I. a. (2004). The effect of organisational culture and leadership style on job satisfaction and organisational commitment: A cross-national comparison. *Journal of Management Development*, 23, 321-338.
- Darling, J., & Leffel, A. (2012). Developing the Leadership Team in an Entrepreneurial Venture: A Case Focusing on the Importance of Styles. *Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship*, 355-371.
- deshpande, F., & Webster, R. (1989). "Organizational Culture and Marketing: Defining the Research Agenda. *journal of marketing*, 53, 3-15.
- Douglas, T., & Fredendall, L. (2004). Evaluating the Deming management model of total quality in services. *Decision Sciences*, 35(3), 393-422.
- Dvir, T. E. (2002). Impact of transformational leadership on follower. *Academy of management journal*, 45(4), 735-744.
- Explorable.com. (2009). Convenience Sampling.
- Farahnak, L., Ehrhart, M., Torres, E., & Aarons, G. (2019). The Influence of Transformational Leadership and Leader Attitudes on Subordinate Attitudes and Implementation Success. *Leadership & Organizational Studies*.
- ferreira, d. O. (2015). The impact of transformational leadership style on on org citizenship behaviour. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 20(3), 493-504.
- Fields, D. (2002). Taking the measure of work: A guide to validated scales for organizational research and diagnosis. *sage publications*.
- Fink, A. (1995). How to Sample in Surveys. Vol. 6. London:.
- franks, s. a. (2012). Religion as the Third Rail of Ethics Education. *Journal of Business Ethics Education*, 9, 395-410.
- Ghasabeh, M. R. (2015). The emerging role of transformational leadership. *Journal of Developing Areas*, 49(6), 459-467.
- Grossman, R. (2000). Emotions at work. *Health Forum Journal*, 43(5), 18-22.
- Henry, G. (1990). T. Practical Sampling. Vol. 21. London: Sage Publications.
- Henseler J., R. C. (2015). "A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modelling", *J. of the Acad. Mark. Sci*, Vol (43), 115-135.
- Henseler, H. &. (2016). Using PLS path modeling in new technology research: updated guidelines, *Industrial Management & Data Systems*.
- Kogut, B., & Zander, U. (1996). What firms do? Coordination, identity and learning. *Organization Science*, 7, 502-518.
- Kouzes, J., & Posner, B. (2006). *The leadership challenge* (Vol. 3). San Francisco: John Wiley & Sons.
- Kumar, R. (2005). RESEARCH METHODOLOGY. *SAGE Publications Ltd*, 441.
- Lagowska, U., Jacob, J., Sobral, F., & Goldszmidt, R. (2018 July). Authentic vs. Ethical Leadership and Social Identity Threat: the Role of Social Distance. *Academy of Management*, 2018.
- Lewis, P., & Kuhnert, K. (1987). Transactional and Transformational Leadership: A Constructive/Developmental Analysis. *The Academy of Management Review*, 12(4), 648-657.
- Lim, B. C., & PloyHart, R. E. (2004). Transformational leadership: relations to the five-factor model and team performance in typical and maximum contexts. *journal of applied psychology*, 89, 610-21.
- Lincoln, Y. S. (2000). Paradigmatic controversies, contradictions and emerging confluences. In N.
- Locke, E., & Latham, G. (1990). Work motivation and satisfaction: Light at the end of the tunnel. *Psychological science*, 1(4), 240-246.

- MacKenzie, S., Podsakoff, P., & Rich, G. (2001). Transformational and transactional leadership and salesperson performance. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 29(2), 115.
- Manzoor, F., Wei, L., Nurunnabi, M., Abdul Subhan, Q., Shah, S., & Fallatah, S. (2019). The Impact of Transformational Leadership on Job Performance and CSR as Mediator in SMEs. *Sustainability*, 11(2), 436.
- McCull-Kennedy, J., & Anderson, R. (2005). Subordinate–manager gender combination and perceived leadership style influence on emotions, self-esteem and organizational commitment. *Journal of Business Research*, 58(2), 115-125.
- Megheirkouni, M. (2017). Leadership styles and organizational learning in UK for profit and non-profit sports organizations. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 25(4), 596-612.
- Moran, B. (2013). *Library and Information Center Management*, 9th Edition. CA, 9TH.
- Munaf, S. (2010). Relationship of Transformational, Transactional and Passive/Avoidant. *International Conference on E-business, Management and Economics*, 3, 93-96.
- Myers, M. D. (1997). Qualitative research in information systems.
- Obisi, C. (-2011). EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL AND ITS IMPLICATION FOR. *Australian Journal of Business and Management Research*, 1, 92-97.
- Podsakoff, P., MacKenzie, S., & Bommer, W. (1996). Transformational leader behaviors and substitutes for leadership as determinants of employee satisfaction, commitment, trust, and organizational citizenship behaviors. *Journal of Management*, 22(2), 259-298.
- Posner, H. A. (2015). Religion, religiosity, and leadership practices. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 36, 396-412.
- Rainey, H., & Steinbauer, P. (1999). Galloping elephants: Developing elements of a theory of effective government organizations. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 9(1), 1-32.
- Renz, D., & Herman, R. (10 August 2016). *The Jossey-Bass Handbook of Nonprofit Leadership and Management, Fourth Edition*. Wiley and Sons.
- Riggio, B. & (2006). Transformational Leadership. *Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Inc.*, 2nd.
- Rogel, C. (2014). The 12 Attributes of a Strong Organizational Culture. *BUSINESS JOURNAL*, 7, 654-689.
- Sluss, D. M., & Ashforth, B. E. (2007). Relational identity and identification: Defining ourselves through work relationships. *Academy of Management Review*, 32, 9-32.
- Spiker, B., & Brown, L. (2000). First, Break All the Rules: What the World and Greatest Managers Do Differently. *Management Communication Quarterly*, 14(2), 322.
- Walt, N. A. (2005). An exploration of the relationship between leadership styles and the implementation of transformation. *Journal of Human Resource Management*, 3, 1-10.
- Westley, F., & Mintzberg, H. (1989). Visionary Leadership and Strategic Management. *Strategic Management Journal*, 10, 17-32.
- Yukl, G. (1999). An evaluation of conceptual weaknesses in transformational and charismatic leadership theories. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 10(2), 285-305.
- Yukl, G. (2008). The Importance of Flexible Leadership. *Society for Industrial Organizational Psychology*.
- Zenger, J. H., Folkman, J. R., & Edinger, S. K. (2009). The Inspiring Leader.
- Zhu, W., Chew, I., & Spangler, W. (2005). CEO transformational leadership and organizational outcomes: The mediating role of human-capital-enhancing human resource management. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 16, 39-52.

Author Information

Jalil Ahmed Thebo*

Faculty member, SZABIST Larkana

Qasim Ali Shah

Lecturer, Management Sciences SZABIST Larkana

Juned Ali Shah

Lecturer, Management Sciences SZABIST Larkana

Imran Ahmed Shah

Assistant Professor, ILMA University Karachi

Hassan Jawad Soomro

Professor, Institute of Commerce and Management Shah Abdul Latif University Khairpur

Ghulam Akbar Khaskheli

Affiliated, Institute of Commerce and Management, Shah Abdul Latif University Khairpur